

Numerical Modeling of Impact Performance of Integrated Multi-layered Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT: The goal of this work is to analyze the ballistic performance of multimaterial systems using a detailed finite element analysis. Recently developed automatic geometry generation algorithm for composite materials is utilized to study the ballistic properties of ceramic sphere composites with textile composite backings. A detailed study of a new multiphase design concept is presented using a full finite element discretization method that shows that although ceramic spheres embedded in epoxy exhibit a slightly lower energy absorption than the monolithic ceramic at the same areal density, they provide the advantage of ease of complex shape conformable manufacturing. A comparison with ballistic experiments on such material demonstrates that the analysis captures several aspects of this phenomenon.

KEYWORDS: multiphase composite materials, textile composites, numerical modeling, ballistic impact.

INTRODUCTION

As the weapon designers were constantly improving the terminal effects of their projectiles, the armors were becoming thicker and heavier. The increased weight of the armor reduces the mobility of its user. Hence, armor materials research strives to find solutions for the major problems associated with armors: penetrability, weight and expense [5, 7, 11].

Experiments with lightweight armor systems are essential to improve the understanding of the armor system penetration mechanisms. Unfortunately, the complexity and briefness of the impact event make instrumentation and measurements very difficult, and experiment becomes expensive and time consuming [9, 11]. On the other hand, it is evident that the complexity of the modern light armor construction has increased many fold and so did its structural analysis. With such complex designs the number of independent parameters is very large. To complement and perhaps guide the necessary experimental evaluation of such system, it is essential to develop a computational methodology that may lead us to an improved understanding of the relative significance of the various design parameters. The key difficulty of this approach is the associated computational complexity both in terms of geometry and material models [2-4].

In this work we analyze the ballistic impact on complex structures, such as angle-ply composites, with ceramic facing layer. Moreover, we evaluate the difference in performance between a full ceramic facing versus a set of ceramic spheres embedded in light epoxy. The latter was recently proposed [10] as an alternative to monolithic ceramic in order to provide the feasibility for flexible armor manufacturing without sacrificing its ballistic effectiveness.

The approach presented here considers each material separately. Discrete models for the study of textile composites offer the advantage of using different and more detailed description of material properties for both matrix and fibers, and accurate description of the geometry. In this way, more realistic failure criteria

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can be introduced and the effects of fiber architecture on the dynamic properties of these composites can be assessed.

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

In the search for improved armors, ceramic materials have been considered [1, 2-4, 8, 9]. High stiffness and hardness make them suitable for protective applications. Their brittle behavior and poor tensile strength, however, cause failure and prevent them from absorbing adequate amount of energy during the impact. By supporting the ceramic facing with a ductile back-up plate, the performance of the armor can be dramatically improved [4, 8]. The ballistic limit velocity (v_{50}) is a measure of an armor performance. It is defined as the minimum impact velocity for perforation, or the maximum impact velocity for which the residual velocity is zero.

In this system each component serves a different role. The hard facing layer shatters or blunts the projectile. The backing plate not only absorbs impact energy but also contains the damage in the ceramics and spreads the energy over a larger area.

Due to their high impact resistance and low density, fabric armors are usually employed for personal protection, and considerable research has been directed to the study of the ballistic behavior of laminated, woven, and braided fabrics [6].

In order to defeat higher velocity threats and address the need for lighter weight and complex shape formability, the concept of introducing a hard phase in spherical form, or Multi-layered Design Composite (MDC) was developed (Figure 1, [6, 10]). Ceramic spheres embedded in epoxy can conform complex shapes easily. At the same time, localized damage may be at least to certain extent repairable.

Figure 1 MDC Material Concept

This system offers a level of inhomogeneity that may induce rotation of the projectile; a mechanism widely recognized for reduction of penetration capability [12]. To avoid weak spots in the areas between the spheres, a second layer can be used with the sphere centers placed on top of the interstices of the first layer.

Our main objectives in modeling of Multi-layered Design Composites are to:

- (a) simulate the ballistic performance of this complex material system;
- (b) attribute significance to the various design parameters such as material properties, and armor architecture;

- (c) evaluate the difference in performance between a full ceramic facing versus a set of ceramic spheres embedded in light epoxy;
- (d) address the role of spherical size, and packing mode in armor ballistic resistance; and
- (e) compare the performance of the spherical facing system with respect to the position of impact in anticipation of non-uniform response due to non-alignment of projectile and spheres.

This type of analysis also provides information regarding the extent of the damage zone in the neighborhood of impact in both facing and backing materials.

Angle-ply laminates are usually formed as multi-layered sheets placed under different angles. In this work, because of computational efficiency, hundreds of angle-ply layers are represented as a two-layer angle-ply laminate considering yarn as an anisotropic continuum.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Several sets of simulations were performed in order to evaluate effects of ceramic facing (monolithic vs. spherical), size of spheres (6.35mm, 9mm, and 12.7mm), and impact site (Figure 2), on armor ballistic performance. In order to address the role of packing factor, performance of 12.7mm spheres is compared with two layers of 6.35mm spheres, as shown on Figure 2, where the spheres are arranged so that top layer is located at the interstitial position of the bottom layer.

A projectile is modeled as cylinder with the diameter of 7.62mm, and mass of 125 grains, which corresponds to 8g of a 7.62 NATO projectile.

**Figure 2 Simulated Impact Sites on Ceramic Facing Model
Composed of Two Layers of 6.35mm Spheres**

Typical FE model of an integrated MDC is presented on Figure 3. The finite element mesh was generated using both, newly developed FE-FGM algorithm [6], and ABAQUS EXPLICIT commercial finite element code (Hibbitt Inc., Rhode Island, 2001).

Figure 3 FE Mesh of Multi-layered Design Composite Model

Material properties used in simulations for both projectile and target, are listed in Table 1. Low density, high strength polymeric fibers, such as aramid (Kevlar[®]) and ultra high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) (Spectra[®]) fibers, have been extensively used in composites for high velocity impact applications such as body armors, vehicles, and other structural and mechanical elements. In this work, the projectile is modeled as elastic-plastic steel material, ceramic facing is assumed to be made of alumina, and the polymer matrix composite backing plate, consisted of Spectra[®] fabric embedded in epoxy matrix. The specific properties used in the simulations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Material Properties Used in Impact Models

Property	Steel	Alumina	Epoxy	Spectra [®]
Density (kg/m ³)	7800	3900	1200	970
Modulus (GPa)	210	350	3.45	268
Poisson's ratio	0.3	0.22	0.35	0.4
Plasticity σ (MPa), ϵ_{pl}	1240, 0.00 1550, 0.010	2400	50	3000
Tensile strength (MPa)	/	360	/	/
Strain to failure	0.025	/	0.05	0.03

A simple, strain-to-failure model was used to represent the failure of both epoxy and textile reinforcement (ABAQUS, Hibbitt Inc.). When the equivalent plastic strain at a material point reaches the plastic failure strain, ϵ_f^{pl} , the material point is failed. If all of the material points in the element fail, the element loses its ability to resist any further load and, hence, it is removed from the mesh. The ductile failure model is based on a damage-Von Mises plasticity theory with isotropic hardening.

Alumina was modeled to fail at a tensile stress of 360MPa. At this value of stress, the material underwent brittle failure.

In order to make truthful comparison, the ballistic effectiveness of different ceramic plates, the thickness (t) of monolithic tile was selected to match areal density (A_p) of specific spherical ceramic facing system (Table 2).

Table 2 Characteristics of Different Ceramic Facing Models

Ceramic Model		6.35mm	2x6.35mm	9mm	12.7mm
Ceramic spheres embedded in epoxy	m [kg]	0.0725	0.145	0.11	0.145
	A_p [kg/m ²]	12.675	25.35	21	25.35
	V_f [%]	30	30	30	30
Monolithic tile	m [kg]	0.14	0.28	0.2	0.28
	A_p [kg/m ²]	24.75	49.5	35	49.5
Equivalent monolithic ceramic plate with equal areal density	t [mm]	3.25	6.5	5.35	6.5

Simulations of 300m/s impact predict that absorbed energy of monolithic ceramic plate would be comparable to that of spherical ceramic plates (Figure 4).

In the models presented here, facing layer have volume fraction of 30%. More closed packed spherical facing would further enhance ballistic resistance bringing it even closer to that of monolithic ceramic plate.

Figure 4 Absorbed Energy of Different Ceramic Plate Models

For the model of 9mm ceramic spheres embedded in epoxy, results show, for both impacts between two and four spheres, lower residual velocity and better penetration resistance than in the case of central impact. Time history of the residual velocity as a function of impact site, is presented on Figure 5.

When the impact site is located between 4 spheres (point three on Figure 2), the energy absorption is highest, because all four spheres participate and resist perforation. Minimum energy absorption is observed when impact occurs directly on the center of one sphere because the surrounding spheres do not contribute substantially in energy absorption.

Figure 5 Effect of Impact Site on Velocity History for a 9mm Thick Facing with Ceramic Spheres

In addition, simulations of 300m/s impact (Figure 6), shows that packing factor of proposed multi-layered spherical ceramics embedded in light epoxy plays important role in optimization of armor ballistic resistance.

Figure 6 Absorbed Energy of Two Layers of 6.35mm Spheres with Different Stacking Sequence

Different stacking sequence contributes to more closed packed spherical ceramic facing, which as a result, would significantly enhance armor ballistic limit. Absorbed impact energy is greater in the case when layers of ceramic spheres are shifted compared to the model where they are simply placed one on the top of the other, because larger number of spheres resist projectile penetration.

It is to assume that hard ceramic facing layer, composed of spherical particles, would introduce additional defeat mechanism by changing the direction of impacting projectile during penetration. Indeed, simulations have shown (Figure 7 where epoxy phase of a facing plate is removed, so that penetration and projectile yawing could be visualized), that even for slightly asymmetric course of impact (0.5mm off the point between two spheres), projectile changes the direction by deflecting on the particulate ceramic facing, considerably losing its initial velocity (Figure 8).

Figure 7 Superimposed Un-deformed (Green) and Deformed Model (in White) Showing Considerable Projectile Re-direction During Impact

This is very important characteristic of spherical ceramic facing, since the probability of hitting in between the spheres is much higher than central hit. In that sense, the central impact under normal angle, although much less possible, could be considered as a worst-case scenario of ballistic event.

Figure 8 Projectile's Yawing Results in Better Armor Penetration Resistance

Finally, Ballistic resistance of MDC with spherical ceramic facing backed with angle-ply composite plate was compared with that of an armor system composed of monolithic ceramic tile with the same areal density, (Figure 9). Impact velocity was 300m/s, and both plates were perforated, but residual velocity, and impact resistance showed to be similar.

Figure 9 Effect of Ceramic Facing on Ballistic Resistance of MDC Models

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULT

In order to validate numerical models and results, high velocity impact test on integral Multi-layered Design Composite plate was carried out*. A one stage 25.4mm gas-gun was used. The projectile was recovered after it had perforated the target. The residual velocity and the residual mass of the projectile were measured, and the differential kinetic energy was calculated, yielding the energy absorbed by the target.

Backing plate of the target panel was 16mm thick angle-ply (0/90) Spectra® reinforced composite, and facing was made of 6.35mm (1/4") ceramic spheres embedded in light epoxy. The panel dimensions are 30.5cmx30.5cmx2.3cm (12"x12"x0.9") with the mass of 2867.6g.

The initial velocity of cylindrical, flat-ended, Tungsten heavy alloy projectile with the mass of 10.712g was 920m/s, and the measured residual velocity after complete penetration was 735m/s. Figure 10 shows high-speed photography of a ballistic test (the time interval between frames is 5μsec).

Figure 10 High-speed Photograph of the Ballistic Impact Test

* The ballistic test was performed at UCSD's Center of Excellence for Advanced Materials (CEAM) directed by Professor Sia Nemat-Nasser.

The experiments were performed by Mr. Jon Isaacs in collaboration with graduate student Mr. Sai Sarva, and the results were summarized by graduate student Mr. Thomas Plaisted.

Based on experimental results, a finite element model is made with the same combination of materials: 6.35mm alumina spherical facing (tetragonal arrangement), and 16mm thick, 0°/90° angle-ply Spectra®/epoxy backing (Vf=50%), with the areal density corresponding to that of the armor sample.

Figure 11 shows FE model during impact simulation with 10μsec step difference. It is important to note that due to complexity of a model, and limitations in terms of the level of discretization, in order to limit the CPU time of a modern PC Pentium 4 machine, adopted MDC model has different packing factor of ceramic facing compared to that of a tested sample. Thus, given results and comparisons, as a first approximation, have only qualitative character.

Figure 11 Material Damage in Different Phases of Target During Impact Simulation

Compared with high-speed photograph of ballistic test, simulation accurately predicts projectile penetration and both level and shape of the backing plate deformation. During the simulation, the shattering of ceramic spheres behind the penetrating projectile could also be visualized.

High-speed photography and residual velocity data (obtained from magneto coil sensors) indicate that the projectile did indeed tumble during perforation through target. This is probably a result of the projectiles successfully being deflected off the aluminum spheres. The recovered projectile confirms that it underwent erosion during penetration. However, there is also an indication of shattering on the sides of the projectile, which again could be a result of oblique penetration due to tumbling, as numerical simulations predicted it.

In addition, impact simulation has predicted residual velocity of 756m/s, which is close to one measured in the test.

CONCLUSION

Ballistic resistance of MDC with facing layer of ceramic spheres embedded in epoxy is showed to have lower ballistic resistance to that of solid ceramic tile. As a result of presented simulations, it can be said that with further optimization and parametric studies, especially of spherical size and their packing factor, ceramic spheres offer potential to replace the conventional ceramic tiles to reduce weight and cost without sacrificing its ballistic effectiveness.

Simulations have shown additional defeat mechanism of proposed spherical facing ceramic layer, by changing the direction of impacting projectile during penetration.

Detailed numerical modeling, presented here, compared to experimental results, showed to provide even more information on behavior of different target constituents during ballistic impact. No doubt that computer simulations represent important step in better understanding of different geometric and material ef-

fects in armor ballistic resistance, and opens the possibility of advanced parametric and sensitivity studies critical for advancement in the field of modern armor protective systems.

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